

Synergistic Enhancement of Supercapacitors with Cobalt–Copper Bimetal–Organic Framework

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Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), as high-potential electrode materials for applications in supercapacitors, have received significant attention recently. Unfortunately, MOF materials still suffer from unsatisfactory specific capacitances due to poor conductivity and limited redox active sites. Herein, a novel cobalt–copper-based bimetal–organic framework (CoCu-MOF) is synthesized by a bottom-up synthesis strategy, the material properties systematically characterized, and finally investigated as a supercapacitor electrode material. The synthesized CoCu-MOF presents a high specific surface area of $62.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and 83% of the copper ions attains the +1 oxidation state contributing to the formation of additional redox active sites and leading to the formation of dual-redox sites. The CoCu-MOF displays an excellent specific capacitance of 618 F g^{-1} at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , which is more than twice that of Co-MOF and four times that of Cu-MOF. The CoCu-MOF retains 75% of its original capacitance after 3000 charge–discharge cycles at the current density of 1 A g^{-1} . Overall, this work demonstrates how the bimetallic synergistic strategy can effectively enhance the electrochemical properties of MOFs by providing a higher specific surface area and by the introduction of dual redox sites.

consumption and production of energy.^[1] Global energy crisis has raised concerns about the generation and consumption of electrical energy, highlighting the significance of developing new storage devices with a higher capacity than the existing technologies. Supercapacitors (SCs) have garnered significant interest in the energy storage field for their remarkable electrochemical characteristics, including high power density, extended cycle life, and cost-effective maintenance.^[2–4]

The electrode materials of SCs, such as carbon materials, metal oxides, metal sulfides, metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), and so on, have been extensively investigated in recent years.^[4–8] Carbon materials are widely utilized as electrode materials for SCs due to high specific surface area, rich pore structure, outstanding conductivity, and chemical stability.^[5] Graphite, serving as a conventional electrode employed in Li-ion-based batteries, exhibits high energy

capacity, fast charging–discharging rate, and long lifecycle.^[8] However, it suffers from a low specific capacitance, which is unsatisfied for SCs.^[8] Metal oxides have a high energy density, excellent durability, and capacitance retention, whereas they present relatively low conductivity and capacitance.^[6,8,9] Compared with metal oxides, metal sulfides exhibit an apparent improvement in the specific capacitance, which is due to the low charge transfer resistance and the fast ion diffusion rate.^[10] Unfortunately, low cycling stability and volume change during charge/discharge processes for metals oxides and transition metal sulfides limit their applications in SCs.^[8,11] MOFs, a functional material comprising metal ions and organic linkers, have widely aroused attention in the field of energy storage due to large specific area, tunable size and pore volume, and incorporated metal centers, especially in SCs.^[12,13] The electrochemical properties of single-metal MOFs with different metal species were widely investigated for applications in SCs.^[14–23] Although MOFs has an enormous potential as electrode candidates, some inherent defects, such as poor electrical conductivity,^[24] the relative weak stability,^[25] and low redox-site density,^[26] lead to a limited specific capacitance. To solve these shortcomings, researches have proposed some strategies, such as enhancing electron transport by synthesized layered and thin MOF nanosheets^[19] and improving specific surface by tuning the hierarchical porous structure.^[18] In addition,

1. Introduction

Energy is crucial for the progress of humanity. The global economy and environment are significantly impacted by the

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the mixed-metal method is also developed to strength the specific capacitance.^[27–32] Nevertheless, it is still essential to explore new bimetal MOFs and investigate their chemical properties, because the relevant reports about bimetal MOFs are limited and their chemical performance needs to be improved.

In this work, we synthesized a flower-like bimetal CoCu-MOF material in a glass tube by a bottom-up strategy. For comparison, Co-MOF and Cu-MOF materials were also synthesized using the same method. The electrochemical performances for SCs were investigated for these MOF materials in a three-electrode system. It was observed that the CoCu-MOF material provides a high specific capacitance of 618 F g^{-1} at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , which is higher than two times of Co-MOF and four times of Cu-MOF. The improved performance of the CoCu-MOF should be closely related to the increased specific surface area, the decreased electrical conductivity, and more active sites provided by dual-redox-sites compared with that of the Co-MOF. This study illustrates the efficacy of a mixed-metal synergistic strategy in precisely modulating the physical–chemical properties of MOFs, consequently enhancing their electrochemical performance.

2. Results and Discussion

Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF materials were synthesized in a glass tube by a bottom-up strategy in this work. The synthesis of the CoCu-MOF material was based on the diffusion-mediated regulation of MOF growth kinetics. As schematized in Figure 1a₁, the synthesis medium comprised N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and CH₃CN separated in three liquid layers of different mixing ratios and resulting different densities. The topmost (iii) layer contained Cu(CH₃COO)₂ and Co(CH₃COO)₂, the bottom layer 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic (BDCA), while a middle layer of solvent separated them (ii). Under static conditions at 40 °C, Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ cations, as well as BDCA linker precursors, diffused into the middle solvent layer, where the CoCu-MOF formed locally and grew, as illustrated in Figure 1a₂,a₃. The synthesized CoCu-MOF material naturally sedimented at the bottom of the container (Figure 1a₄). Cu-MOF and Co-MOF were synthesized via the same synthesis methodology.

The morphology of Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF was characterized by scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy. As presented in Figure 1b,c, the Cu-MOF consisted of square lamellae with lateral dimensions

Figure 1. a) Synthesis scheme of CoCu-MOF material, b) TEM image of the Cu-MOF, c,d) SEM images of the Co-MOF and the CoCu-MOF, e,f) HAADF-STEM images of the CoCu-MOF material at different magnifications, and g) elemental mappings of C, Cu, O, and Co.

of 50–200 nm, while the Co-MOF consisted of irregular lamellae at a microscale. The different structures clearly indicated the modulation of MOF growth kinetics following the introduction of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} , respectively. Next, CoCu-MOF with a Co:Cu ratio of 6 presented a flower-like structure composed of nanosheets with thicknesses in the 100–150 nm range (Figure 1d–f). Elemental mapping of the CoCu-MOF revealed a homogeneous and uniform distribution of C, O, Cu, and Co elements (Figure 1g). The Co:Cu ratio was also analyzed by scanning transmission electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDS) (Figure S1, Supporting Information), showing a Co:Cu ratio of 6.16, close to the Co:Cu feeding ratio of 6. The feeding ratio of Co:Cu was significant for the formation of the special flower-like structure. When decreasing the Co:Cu ratio from 10 to 4, we observed that the flower-like structures became larger and contained denser nanosheets, as revealed by optical imaging in Figure S2, Supporting Information. The Co:Cu ratio of the CoCu-MOF was further analyzed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) (Table 1), exhibiting results similar to STEM-EDS. The CoCu-MOF with a Co:Cu ratio of 6 was selected for an in-depth study of structural properties and electrochemical performance.

The flower-like structure of CoCu-MOF with regular and small nanosheets featured a specific surface area of $62.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, much larger than that of Co-MOF ($24.3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), and a slightly larger total pore volume (Table 1). The Cu-MOF presented the largest total surface area and total pore volume due to its small and thin nanosheet structure. Typical type IV isotherms, observed from the N_2 sorption isotherms (Figure 2a), indicate the presence of a mesoporous pore structure. The N_2 uptake at a relative pressure between 0.8 and 1.0 exhibited a H1-type hysteresis loop, which is indicative of cylindrical pores with a “house-of-cards” structure.^[33,34] The average pore diameters of the Cu-MOF,

Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF are 28.0, 14.8, and 18.7 nm, respectively.

Figure 2b shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of each material with the representative peaks of CoCu-MOF entirely different from those of the Co-MOF and the Cu-MOF, indicating the formation of new crystal structures. In the XRD of the bimetallic CoCu-MOF, there are no peaks between 20° – 30° corresponding to the Cu-MOF structure, and the absence of ligand peaks indicates that a 2D nanosheet structure may have been synthesized. The CoCu-MOF structure is therefore most likely formed by the aggregation of 2D nanosheets rather than a 3D MOF structure despite the 3D flower-like structure observed by SEM.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were measured to study the chemical bond formations in the MOF materials, as shown in Figure 3. The peaks in the wavenumber range of 1690 – 1667 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the stretching vibration of the C=O bond.^[35] The peaks at 1574 and 1384 cm^{-1} are thought to be the asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of COO^- , respectively, indicating the deprotonation of COOH upon MOF formation and the bond linkage between Cu/Co metals and BDC ligands.^[36,37] In addition, the apparent peaks in the range of 747 – 733 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the stretching vibration of Co-O-H or Cu-O-H .^[35]

The oxidation states of Cu and Co species were characterized by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (Figure 4). As shown in Figure 4c, both Co-MOF and CoCu-MOF materials exhibited the characteristic Co 2p peaks. The characteristic peaks at 780.5 and 796.2 eV are attributed to Co 2p_{3/2} and Co 2p_{1/2} of Co^{2+} species, respectively, while the peaks at 781.7 and 797.4 eV correspond to Co 2p_{3/2} and Co 2p_{1/2} of Co^{3+} species, respectively.^[38] The fit results indicate that the Co-MOF and the CoCu-MOF materials have a similar $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{2+}$ ratio of ≈ 2.5 in the two

Table 1. Brunhauer–Emmett–Teller and XRF analysis of Cu–MOF, Co–MOF, and CoCu–MOF materials.

MOF materials	Specific surface area [$\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$]	Total pore volume [$\text{cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$]	Average pore diameter [nm]	Cu [wt%]	Co [wt%]	Co:Cu [atom ratio]
Cu–MOF	80.9	0.33	28.0	21.6	0	0
Co–MOF	24.3	0.10	14.8	0	19.6	100
CoCu–MOF	62.4	0.14	18.7	3.1	18.1	6.2

Figure 2. a) N_2 sorption isotherms and b) XRD patterns of Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF materials.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF materials.

MOF materials. Interestingly, a clear difference in oxidation states of Cu species was observed for the Cu-MOF and the CoCu-MOF. According to previous research, the characteristic peaks at 932.8 and 952.6 eV can be attributed to Cu 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} of Cu⁺ species, whereas peaks at 934.4 and 954.4 eV correspond to Cu 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} of Cu²⁺ species, respectively.^[39,40] As shown in Figure 4d and Table S1, Supporting Information, the percentages of Cu²⁺ and Cu⁺ for Cu-MOF are 82% and 18%, respectively. However, the percentages of Cu²⁺ and Cu⁺ for CoCu-MOF are 17% and 83%, respectively. The results indicate that Cu-MOF is mainly composed of

Cu²⁺, while CoCu-MOF is dominated by Cu⁺. The existence of Cu⁺ is likely to promote the construction of new redox active sites.

The electrochemical properties of the Cu-MOF, the Co-MOF, and the CoCu-MOF materials were investigated using a three-electrode system in 2 M KOH electrolyte. As shown in Figure 5a–c, the cyclic voltammetry (CV) was implemented with a potential range from –0.1 to 0.5 V at scan rates from 10 to 100 mV s^{–1} for Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF electrodes, respectively. CV curves of the Cu-MOF and the Co-MOF electrodes presented one oxidation peak and one reduction peak, demonstrating their Faradaic features. Interestingly, CV curves of the CoCu-MOF electrode exhibited two oxidation peaks (about 0.31 and 0.35 V) and two reduction peaks (about 0.16 and 0.22 V) at low scan rates. It can be inferred that Cu⁺ is easily converted to Cu²⁺, thus constructing a new redox active site. The two redox peaks might be attributed to the conversion between Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ and between Cu⁺ and Cu²⁺. The dual-redox sites contribute to provide more active sites for the redox reaction, thus improving the electrochemical performance.^[26] Furthermore, the CoCu-MOF presented an increased scanning area of CV curves, indicating a higher specific capacitance. Figure 5d–e shows the charge–discharge curves of the three MOF materials. During the charge–discharge processes, the CoCu-MOF electrode presented smooth tilted voltage curves, demonstrating a good pseudocapacitive behavior with a rapid I–V response.^[41] The specific capacitances at current densities from 1 to 20 A g^{–1} were calculated and presented in Figure 5f. The CoCu-MOF material showed the longest discharge time, revealing the largest specific capacitance reaching 618 F g^{–1} at

Figure 4. a) Survey spectra, b) O 1s, c) Co 2p, and d) Cu 2p XPS patterns of Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF materials.

Figure 5. Electrochemical properties of the MOF materials. CV curves for a) Cu-MOF, b) Co-MOF, and c) CoCu-MOF. Charge–discharge profiles for d) CoCu-MOF at different current densities and e) for all three materials at 20 A g^{-1} . f) Specific capacitance, g) EIS, h) cycling performance, and i) comparison between specific capacitances for MOF materials in literature and in this work.

a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , which is more than two times that of the Co-MOF and four times of the Cu-MOF. A high specific capacitance of 436 F g^{-1} was still obtained at a high current density of 20 A g^{-1} , implying that the CoCu-MOF material had a good rate capability. It can also be observed that Co-MOF presents a higher specific capacitance than Cu-MOF, which is due to the better redox reaction ability of the Co-MOF material.^[20] These results indicate that the strategies of mixed-metal MOF can effectively improve the specific capacitance in comparison to the single-metal MOF materials.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a significant indicator for evaluating the conductivity properties of electrode materials. The EIS data were collected with an AC voltage of 10 mV amplitude in a frequency range from 1 MHz to 100 mHz (Figure 5g). The CoCu-MOF semicircle in the high-frequency ranges was smaller than those of the Cu-MOF and the Co-MOF, revealing the smallest charge transfer resistance

(R_{ct}) of the CoCu-MOF electrode. The lowest R_{ct} is likely related to the introduction of Cu^+ in the CoCu-MOF electrode materials, which facilitates faster charge transport. The equivalent series resistance (ESR) can be obtained from the real axis intercept in the high-frequency range of the Nyquist plots. The CoCu-MOF presented the lowest ESR value of 1.48Ω , as compared to 1.52Ω for Co-MOF and 1.75Ω for Cu-MOF, indicating its superior electrical conductivity. Next, galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) tests of 3000 cycles were executed at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} to investigate the cycle stability and performance durability of the CoCu-MOF material. As shown in Figure 4h, a capacitance retention of 75% of the initial value was retained after 3000 cycles, suggesting that the cycling stability needs to be further improved.

Combining the advantages of each component, the mixed-metal MOF can effectively improve the electrochemical performances compared with the single-metal MOF materials. Co-MOF

exhibited a higher specific capacitance than Cu-MOF due to its better redox reaction ability, while the CoCu-MOF material exhibited an even better electrochemical performance after the introduction of Cu species. The increased electrochemical performance of the novel CoCu-MOF can be explained by the increased specific surface area of $62.4\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, which is significantly larger than that of the Co-MOF ($24.3\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$). Furthermore, the prevalence of Cu^+ over Cu^{2+} in the CoCu-MOF is more favorable for the formation of new redox active sites to form dual-redox sites. Finally, the higher electrical conductivity of the CoCu-MOF contributes to a faster electric transfer and ion diffusion, thus decreasing the impedance. Taken together, this led to an obvious increase in electrochemical performance. In Figure 5i the specific capacitances for different bimetal MOF materials reported in literature and in this work are summarized and compared.^[26,28,30–32] The CoCu-MOF synthesized in this work presents a higher specific capacitance than those reported for Zn/Cu-MOF and Ni/Cu-MOF.

3. Conclusion

This study presents a novel bimetallic CoCu-MOF synthesized using a convenient bottom-up method, which provides an approach to address the challenges faced in the use of MOFs as SC electrode materials. The CoCu-MOF exhibited a significantly higher specific surface area of $62.4\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ compared to single-metal Co-MOF of $24.3\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$. The incorporation of copper into the framework resulted in a high Cu^+ percentage of 83%, facilitating the formation of new redox-active sites. This led to the formation of dual-redox sites, effectively providing a greater number of active sites for redox reactions. As a result, the CoCu-MOF demonstrated outstanding electrochemical performance, with a specific capacitance of 618 F g^{-1} at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , surpassing that of Co-MOF by twice and Cu-MOF by four times. Moreover, CoCu-MOF maintained 75% of its original capacitance after 3000 charge–discharge cycles. Overall, these findings underscore the effectiveness of the bimetallic synergistic strategy in enhancing the electrochemical properties of MOFs, offering promising prospects for their practical application in SCs.

4. Experimental Section

Materials and Chemicals: All chemicals were used as received without further purification. $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid (BDCA), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), acetonitrile (CH_3CN), and KOH were acquired from Aladdin Co., Ltd., (Shanghai, China), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, $\geq 99.5\%$) was obtained from Micxy Chemical Co., Ltd., (Chengdu, China). Nickel foam (110 mesh per inch) was purchased from Chuandong Chemical Co., Ltd., (Chongqing, China). Carbon black was purchased from Cabot Corporation (Boston, USA). Deionized water was used in all reactions.

Synthesis of Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF Materials: Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, and CoCu-MOF materials were synthesized in a glass tube by a bottom-up strategy. The synthesis of CoCu-MOF (Co:Cu = 6:1) is described as an example. A linker solution with 25 mg of H_2BDC (corresponding BDCA amount) dissolved in a mixture of 2 mL DMF and 1 mL CH_3CN was poured into the bottom of the tube. Over this solution, a mixture of 1 mL DMF and 1 mL CH_3CN was slowly added to prevent premature mixing of the two solutions containing the precursors. Finally, a metal

precursor solution composed of 37 mg $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 5 mg $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in a mixture of 1 mL DMF, and 2 mL CH_3CN was carefully added to the tube as the top layer. The synthesis proceeded at 40°C for 12 h in static conditions, and the resulting precipitate was collected by centrifugation and washed consecutively three times with DMF (1 mL each step) followed by another five times with CHCl_3 (1 mL each step). The resulting material was dried at 60°C for 3 h under house vacuum ($\approx 10\text{ kPa}$). The product yields of the Cu-MOF, Co-MOF, CoCu-MOF materials were 95%, 93%, and 87%, respectively.

Materials Characterizations: SEM (Nova NanoSEM) was employed to study the morphology of the samples. High-angle-annular dark-field-scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF–STEM, Talos-F20 $^\circ\text{C}$) was further used to observe the morphology and identify the elemental composition of the samples. Before TEM observation, the specimens were prepared by applying a few drops of the MOF chloroformic suspensions on a carbon-coated nicked grid and letting it dry. Nitrogen adsorption–desorption measurements were performed on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 HD 88 surface area and porosity analyzer. FTIR spectra with a range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were collected with a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer at room temperature by diluting samples in KBr. The Co and Cu contents of the CoCu-MOF samples were determined by XRF analysis. The XRF was conducted on a Shimadzu XRF-1800 fluorescence spectrometer coupled with a Rh radiation source at 40 kV and 70 mA and with scintillation counters and gas flow proportional counters as detectors. XRD measurements were carried out using a Bruker diffractometer with Cu radiation (40 kV, 120 mA). XPS was acquired on a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha spectrometer using an Al K α ($h\nu = 1486.6\text{ eV}$) monochromatic small-spot X-ray source. All binding energies were referenced to the C1s line at 284.6 eV.

Electrochemical Measurements: Electrochemical properties of the samples were evaluated on a CHI 660 E electrochemical workstation with a standard three electrode test pool containing 2 M KOH as the electrolyte. The three-electrode configuration consisted of Ag/AgCl as electrode, platinum wire as counter electrode, and a nickel foam electrode as working electrode. For the preparation of working electrode, a mixture containing 70 wt% active materials, 20 wt% acetylene black, and 10 wt% PVDF binder was mixed. Prior to electrochemical deposition, Ni foam was cut into pieces of $10 \times 20\text{ mm}^2$ and cleaned by ultrasonication in 3 M HCl, deionized water, and absolute ethanol successively. CV, GCD, and EIS were studied to determine the electrochemical performance of the nickel foam electrodes. CV was performed with a potential range from -0.1 to 0.5 V at a scan rate from 10 to 100 mV s^{-1} . GCD was carried out in a potential range from -0.1 to 0.45 V . The EIS data was collected with an AC voltage of 10 mV amplitude in the frequency range from 1 MHz to 100 mHz.

The specific capacitance (C , F g^{-1}) was obtained from the GCD data according to Equation (1).

$$C = I\Delta t / m\Delta V \quad (1)$$

where I (A) is the discharge current, Δt (s) is the discharge time, m is the mass of active materials on the electrode, and ΔV (V) is potential window during the discharge process.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Keywords

CoCu-metal-organic frameworks, dual-redox-sites, electrical conductivities, supercapacitors

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